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ASSESSMENT OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING AS A WORK METHODOLOGY FOR AIR NAVIGATION STUDENTS.

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ABSTRACT

Motivation is considered to be a crucial factor in the teaching-learning process in Aerospace Engineering, especially due to the difficulty of the courses taught. The application of active methodologies, focused on student learning, can increase students' motivation, and improve their learning, helping them to persevere through a challenging workload. In this regard, previous studies have shown how the implementation of the Project-Based Learning methodology as a working tool in various disciplines is motivating and facilitates the integration of courses and their success in student learning. This work presents the results, in terms of student satisfaction, of the application of this methodology in various courses of the module Air Navigation Specific Technology, consisting of the development of an airport project considering its associated infrastructures and procedures. The results of the global data collection survey are analysed in order to identify trends. We included open-ended questions in a questionnaire where the students could express their impressions, problems, suggestions for improvement, etc. Through these techniques, in addition to students' satisfaction, other features such as dedication time or problems in developing the project are also analysed to complete the project appraisal.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

The bachelor's degree in Aerospace Engineering from the *Universitat Politècnica de València* (Technical University of Valencia) completes the training of students with a focus on a specific technology (Aeromotors, Aircraft or Air Navigation), which qualifies students for the profession of technical aeronautical engineering. The courses offered in the module Specific Air Navigation Technology provide students with a complement that will allow them to develop their professional work in the general field of technical aeronautical engineering and, in particular, within this particular area. The courses involved in the development of this work are the following (Table 1):

Table 1. PBL Courses on Performance Based Navigation.

Name	Sem.	ECTS	Nº std.
<i>Planificación y Desarrollo de Aeropuertos</i> (Airport Planning and Development)	5	6	14
<i>Navegación Aérea, Cartografía y Cosmografía</i> (Air Navigation, Cartography and Cosmography)	6	4,5	26
<i>Infraestructuras para la Navegación Aérea</i> (Air Navigation Infrastructure)	7	6	22
<i>Gestión del Espacio Aéreo I</i> (Airspace Management I)	7	6	26
<i>Ingeniería de los Sistemas de Navegación Aérea II</i> (Air Navigation Systems Engineering II)	8	6	27
<i>Gestión del Espacio Aéreo II</i> (Airspace Management II)	8	6	31

In the starting situation, the organization of these studies involved the accomplishment of multiple tasks in the different courses, which facilitated the acquisition of the knowledge and competences required for the professional development of students, and which were part of the final evaluation of the courses, together with the completion of open-ended written tests. The diversification, and sometimes overlap, of these tasks required a work overload of the students, who faced these tasks with little motivation.

In the case of training in Aerospace Engineering, motivation is considered as a crucial factor in the learning process and academic performance of students, especially due to the difficulty of the courses taught [1]. It is therefore important to identify the active methodologies that can increase students' motivation and improve their learning, helping them persevere through a challenging workload [2]. Active learning methodologies are based on activities that involve students in such a way that they perform the tasks with a clearly applied focus on the task they carry out, thus achieving a combination of action and reflection that improves the learning capacity of students. Unlike traditional learning approaches, in which the teacher leads the work of students through the teaching of theory lectures and targeted practical sessions, the leading role of students in the teaching-learning process is increasingly required, without ignoring the importance of lectures at the beginning of any process, along with teamwork and students' autonomous work.

The application of new practice-based models particularly benefits engineering education for its essential practice component. In addition, courses in the advanced semesters, in particular those of specific technologies, which have a very technological and systematic nature, are better suited to implement active learning methods such as Project-Based Learning (PBL), which will be the fundamental tool for this process [3]. PBL enhances not only the acquisition by students of the specific competences of each course, but also the development of skills or abilities such as problem-solving, critical thinking, adaptability, capacity for data collection, teamwork, proactivity, among others, increasingly appreciated in the professional field of aviation and aeronautics [4].

In fact, among the benefits of this method it stands out that it fosters autonomous learning, prepares students for qualified jobs, increases motivation, strengthens self-confidence, establishes a connection between academic learning and the real world, offers opportunities for collaboration to build knowledge, improves social and communication skills, increases problem-solving skills, etc. If we also consider the added benefits of collaborative work in terms of increased interaction and critical-thinking skills in the negotiation of solutions, PBL appears to be an ideal strategy for improving the quality of learning [5,6].

The integration of the tasks to be carried out as part of the different subjects involved in the development of this work will enable the students to lead and manage their own project, requiring their own decision-making while constantly having the support of the teachers. The teachers will start the process by identifying the requirements and competences to be acquired through the specified content and skills, yet students will be autonomous in learning the contents and developing the skills. Additionally, project

teamwork will also be encouraged using requirements lists as an interface between teams.

1.2 Objectives

The main objective of this project is to improve the teaching-learning process of students of Specific Air Navigation Technology, using the PBL methodology. To do this, students will develop the design of an airport in accordance with its infrastructure and associated procedures.

The specific objectives, which are intended to be achieved through the application of this didactic methodology, are:

- To increase the motivation of students through the development of an integrated project that implements and contextualises the acquisition of specific competences.
- To improve the ability to apply course content to the professional world, thus expanding the vision of the professional future of students.
- To facilitate the acquisition of skills such as collaborative work and working time management.
- To know the degree of satisfaction of the students regarding the effectiveness of the PBL methodology in the learning process.

With regard to students, it is expected that, upon completion of the airport design project, they will be able to:

- Collect the necessary information in the bibliography and the regulations applicable to airport and infrastructure design.
- Identify the basic functional components of an air navigation system and the needs of on-board and ground equipment for proper operation.
- Apply the theoretical knowledge of the courses involved to professional practice, through the design of the ground side and air side of an airport.
- Calculate the elements required for the development of an airport: runway parameters, electrical networks infrastructure and specific air navigation systems.
- Prepare the report of the design of an airport, including all the necessary documentation, for presentation in oral communication format (presentation or poster).

2 METHODOLOGY

In order to achieve the objectives of the airport design project, the teachers have scheduled some planned open learning activities, based on real cases, associated with the delivery of the project and coordinated between subjects, using the project as a link among them. These activities are intended to facilitate and improve the learning and evaluation process of general, specific and cross-curricular competences. The work of students has been assessed, analyzing and evaluating the achieved results,

both in terms of satisfaction with the PBL methodology as a working tool, and regarding the attainment of the learning outcomes.

The work presented here aims to assess students' perception of the development of skills, and the usefulness and effectiveness of an airport design project.

2.1 Activities

The activities carried out by students throughout the two years of the project are briefly discussed below, indicating the methodology used for their completion, the cross-curricular competences (CTs) developed and their percentage in the final grade of the courses, taking into account that the activities A3, A4 and A5 are carried out in the same courses and activity A9 distributes its 20% weight between activities A7 and A8:

- A1: Airport installation and runway project report (5th semester). Teamwork including an oral presentation through the MICROSOFT TEAMS platform. Involves CT06 – Teamwork and CT08 – Effective Communication. Weight: 30%.
- A2: Study of the reception of radio signals from satellites (6th semester). Teamwork including an oral presentation through the MICROSOFT TEAMS platform. Involves CT08 – Effective Communication and CT11 – Lifelong Learning. Weight: 40%.
- A3: Beaconing project (7th semester). Individual project. Involves CT05 – Design and project and CT07 – Ethical and environmental responsibility. Weight: 10%.
- A4: Electrical installations project (7th semester). Involves CT05 – Design and project and CT07 – Ethical and environmental responsibility. Weight: 10%.
- A5: Radio Navigation project (7th semester). Individual project. Involves CT05 – Design and project and CT07 – Ethical and environmental responsibility. Weight: 10%.
- A6: Radar installations project (7th semester). Individual project. Involves CT09 – Critical thinking and CT10 – Knowledge of contemporary problems. Weight: 20%.
- A7: Communications project (8th semester). Individual report. Involves CT01 – Comprehension and Integration and CT03 – Problem-solving. Weight: 40% (30% + 10% of A9).
- A8: Aeronautical Charts with the design of procedures for approach to the airport (8th semester). Individual report. Involves CT02 – Application and practical thinking and CT13 – Specific instrumental skill. Weight: 50% (40% + 10% of A9).
- A9: Presentation and final evaluation of the airport project (8th semester).

2.2 Instruments

Twenty-six students have participated in the project. Although this is not a very large sample, it is the number of students usually registered in these specific technology courses, so we can consider that the results are reliable. In order to know their evaluation of the project carried out, a survey has been used with a validated questionnaire [7] for assessing their perception of the effectiveness of active participation methodologies in the development of technical and non-technical competences, and in particular of PBL. The aim of this questionnaire has been to assess specific competences of the training profile of the courses taught: general

skills, i.e. instrumental in learning and training; systemic competences, to properly manage the entire task; and interpersonal competences, which allow to keep a good level of social relationship. The 25 items comprised in the questionnaire cover basic skills that any graduate student must achieve, and are answered through a Likert scale including 5 answer options (1 - Strongly disagree; 2 - Disagree; 3 - Neutral; 4 - Agree; 5 - Strongly agree). In addition, three open-ended questions were included in which students could express impressions, problems, difficulties, suggestions for improvement, etc.:

- What aspects could you point out regarding the usefulness of this methodology in improving your learning process?
- What difficulties have you faced when carrying out the different activities of the airport design project?
- Have you found the development of this airport design project motivating? Briefly comment on your answer.

3 RESULTS

Regarding the results obtained in the assessment of students' perception, in this work we deal with those directly related to the objectives of this project. Of the first 5 items of the questionnaire, related to the development of the specific competences of the courses integrated in the project, it is worth pointing out that all participants (26 students) have considered, with the highest score, that the PBL educational methodology helps to contrast the knowledge learned in the classroom with its application in real situations (item 1) and manages to bridge the gap between theory and practice (item 2). 92.3% of students (24 students) completely agree that this methodology facilitates the learning of the course (item 3) and 88.5% of students (23 students) fully agree that it involves participants in their own learning (item 4) and creates an attitude of active participation (item 5).

With regard to the development of cross-curricular competences of the instrumental, systemic and interpersonal categories, the results are presented below for the assessment of the skills: management (items 6, 9 and 16) (Fig. 1), problem solving and critical thinking (items 7 and 8) (Fig. 2), communication (items 12 and 13) (Fig. 3), data collection and instrumental (items 10 and 11) (Fig. 4) and social skills (items 19 and 22) (Fig. 5). These are the items that best represent the competences that have been directly addressed in this project.

Fig. 1. Management skills assessment.

Fig. 2. Problem solving and critical thinking skills assessment.

Fig. 3. Communication skills assessment.

Fig. 4. Instrumental and data collection skills assessment.

Fig. 5. Social skills assessment.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Bearing in mind that the ultimate goal of this project is to facilitate the learning of specific Air Navigation technology subjects, throughout the use of the ABP methodological tool, and to motivate students in the learning process of these subjects; two features have been distinguished. On the one hand, the integration of the competencies provided by different subjects to ensure that the students see them as part of a whole and not in isolation, and look for solutions to their project in such a way that its theoretical components are assimilated; and on the other hand, it is intended to work on full projects development, which will help them to achieve useful competencies for their future professional life as engineers.

In view of the results of the questionnaire, and with the support of the comments provided in the open-ended questions, it can be concluded that the application of the PBL methodology for improving the teaching-learning process of students of Specific Air Navigation Technology has been successful.

Most students have highlighted, above all, the link between courses within a single project and their similarity and connection to their professional future, which has resulted in an increase in motivation. They also stressed that the high level of difficulty of some activities, which could be seen as a negative factor, has motivated them in the problem-solving process. On the other hand, a few students have not found this methodology motivating or effective and have expressed that it has been a great additional workload, and that they have found it difficult to meet the completion deadline of some of the activities, which has caused them a feeling of dissatisfaction.

It is important to highlight the assessment of collaborative work that has been carried out in some of the activities. Although most participants (16 students) have positively assessed the achievement of this goal, many others (10 students) have not considered that the acquisition of this skill has been facilitated. Comments on this have dealt with the current health situation, which does not allow us to perform group tasks in the way we were used to. In this sense, the TEAMS platform has been fundamental to the development of meetings and the presentation of works, and students consider that it has facilitated oral communication by reducing the embarrassment usually associated with speaking to an audience.

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